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POSTER PRESENTATION

ECO-FRIENDLY HYDROPHOBIC TEXTILES: A SHIFT FROM PFAS TO SUSTAINABLE BIO-POLYMERS**Barbara Golja^{1,2}, Blaž Stres², Uroš Novak², Blaž Likozar² and Anja Verbič^{2*}**¹ University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, Slovenia² National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia

Abstract: Identifying efficient and long-lasting textile coatings that can serve as alternatives to toxic per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) is essential for a future free from harmful fluorinated chemicals. For this purpose, a hydrophobic cotton (CO) and polyester (PES) textile fabric was produced using natural biopolymers in the form of microcapsules. The CO and PES samples were coated with dippaddy process and the fabric visual appearance, colour measurements, thickness, morphology and hydrophobicity were evaluated before and after coating. The visual appearance of the fabric did not change significantly with the application of coating, which was confirmed by CIELAB colour measurements. The increase in thickness of the fabric was minimal. The water contact angle increased from highly hydrophilic (<10°) to hydrophobic (above 120°) after the coating application. The research showed that with the use of biopolymers which are environmentally and human health friendly, hydrophobicity of natural and synthetic textile fabrics can be achieved.

Keywords: water-repellence, hydrophobicity, biopolymers, biomaterials, coatings, textile

1. INTRODUCTION

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a large group of more than 4700 (OECD, 2018) synthetic compounds characterized by the presence of strong carbon-fluorine (C-F) bonds, that provide exceptional thermal, chemical, and mechanical stability (Li, 2018). Simultaneous hydrophobic and oleophobic properties make PFAS highly valuable in various industrial applications, such as personal care products, cosmetics, cleaning products, textile coatings for stain and water repellency, food contact materials, adhesives, non-stick pans, medical devices, various membranes, fire-fighting foams, etc. (Panieri, 2022; Gluge, 2020; Gaines, 2023; Kleinman, 2021). However, due to their chemical composition, these compounds are very persistent in the environment, difficult to degrade, and tend to bioaccumulate, leading to significant concerns about potential adverse effects on human health and ecosystems (Wee, 2023). They have been detected in groundwater, surface water and soil worldwide, raising alarms about their longterm effects on the environmental and human exposure (Merino, 2016; Ahrens, 2014; EPA, 2023). People get exposed to PFAS through various pathways, including contaminated water and soil, food chain accumulation, household dust, and others (Karaskova, 2016; Worley, 2017; Lin, 2020; Sadia, 2023; Smalling, 2023), which has been linked to numerous health problems, including reproductive problems, endocrine disruption, immune system effects, infertility, developmental problems in children, weakened immune system, higher cholesterol levels and increased cancer risk (Panieri, 2022; Fenton, 2021; Blake, 2018; EPA, 2023; Bartell, 2021). Because of extensive evidence linking PFAS to serious health effects, addressing PFAS contamination is critical to protect not only the environment but also public health. In response, significant regulatory measures and limitations have been implemented worldwide. Authorities are monitoring the use, manufacture, and disposal of PFAS compounds, and have specified allowable levels of certain PFAS substances in water, soil and air to minimize their release into the environment and reduce associated health risks (EPA, 2023). In addition, regulations have limited the production and use of other PFAS compounds, such as perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) (EPA, 2023). Current initiatives aim to completely eliminate the use of PFAS by banning the production and sale of PFAS-containing textiles and proposing bans or restrictions on up to 12,000 different compounds (NY State department of environmental conservation, 2023; ChemRadar, 2024; Spyraakis, 2023). As a result, industries, including the textile sector, are being urged to find PFAS-free alternatives, that can provide similar benefits without the associated risks, to comply with these regulations. Current synthetic

alternatives to PFAS, such as silicones (Jin, 2018), alkylamines (Lin, 2021), acrylates (Messerschmidt, 2018) and melamine (Zheng, 2020), still have their own environmental concerns. These synthetic compounds may still leave a chemical footprint and may not completely solve the problem of pollution and toxicity. A better and more sustainable option would be to move towards the use of natural, renewable materials, which would provide the desired properties without the harmful environmental impact. The literature review showed, that using biomaterials, hydrophobicity can be achieved either by using low surface energy compounds or by increasing surface roughness (Shahid, 2022). To reduce surface energy, natural compounds such as fatty acids and their salts (Shahid, 2022), or natural waxes like beeswax and carnauba wax have been used (Shahid, 2022). Surface roughening has been achieved through enzyme etching or by applying various nanostructures derived from natural materials (Shahid, 2022), which mimic the lotus leaf effect. Combinations of both approaches can be used to achieve higher levels of hydrophobicity. However, the literature review showed that most of these formulations still involve various chemicals and/or solvents, indicating that the formulations are not completely biomaterial-based and can still pose a level of environment burden and health risks. To address these concerns, it is preferable to use solely natural biomaterials, which can be either chemically modified to achieve hydrophobic properties if they are inherently hydrophilic, or by combining multiple biomaterials to achieve synergistic effects. This is especially promising due to growing interest in biodegradable polymers, derived from renewable sources.

The same approach to hydrophobic coatings development is also used in the Horizon Europe PROPLANET project. Within the project, natural biopolymer-based hydrophobic coatings for textile applications are being developed in alignment with the Safe and sustainable by Design (SsbD) principles to ensure the use of safer and more sustainable materials. One of the ways the project aims to achieve that is by using natural biomaterials in the form of microcapsules (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of a hydrophilic fabric and a hydrophobic fabric achieved with application of coating with microcapsules.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Bleached and mercerized plain weave 100% cotton (CO) woven fabric (185 g/m², warp density 26 threads/cm, weft density 24 threads/cm) from Europrint (Ajdovščina, Slovenia) and polyester (PES) fabric (185 g/m², warp density 21 threads/cm, weft density 17 threads/cm) fabric from Svet Metraže (Ljubljana, Slovenia) were used as substrates for the coating. A suspension of biopolymer-based microcapsules (MC) was prepared using a combination of natural biopolymers. For all of the experiments in the research Milli-Q pure water was used.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Sample preparation

CO and PES fabric samples measuring approximately 35x40 cm were used for coating application, which was carried out using the dippaddy process. The samples were immersed into glass impregnation bath containing coating solution and then squeezed between the rollers of a two-roller foulard (Mathis, Switzerland) to achieve a wet pick up of 80 %, and dried in a laboratory continuous dryer (Mathis, Switzerland) at 40 °C for 5 minutes. The coating formulation was developed as a part of the PROPLANET project and its manufacturing process is protected by the project's intellectual property.

2.2.2 Analysis

Colour measurements

Colour coordinate (CIE L*a*b*) values of the samples were measured using the Datacolor Spectro 1050 reflectance spectrophotometer (Datacolor, Luzern, Switzerland). Measurements were made with a d/8° measurement geometry, under D65 illumination, 10° standard observer, with specular reflectance included, with a 9-mm aperture. Four layers of the sample were used for the measurements and an average of five measurements was reported.

Sample thickness

The thickness of the samples was measured with digital caliper Mitutoyo ID-C112X (Mitutoyo, Japan) with an 8 mm stem diameter and ≤ 1.5N measuring force. Five measurements of each sample were taken, and the average value was reported.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of the samples was analysed using scanning electron microscope JSM-6060 LV (Jeol, Japan). Prior to observation the samples were coated with a thin layer of gold. The coated samples were observed directly after coating. SEM micrographs were taken at a beam voltage 10kV, working distance 16 mm, 30 beam spot size and a magnification of 50x.

Water contact angles (WCA)

The water repellence of the control (uncoated) and coated samples was evaluated by measuring WCA. For this analysis, tensiometer Theta T200 (Biolab Scientific, Gothenburg, Sweden) was used. The static contact angle was determined at 5 seconds after the beginning of the measurement.

3. RESULTS WITH DISCUSSION

The presented research aimed to achieve hydrophobic CO and PES textile substrates by using only natural biopolymers. Our purpose was not only to replace PFAS with other fluorinated compounds, which are currently in broad use and are being phased out by various regulations, but to use only natural substances which are renewable, biodegradable, can be recycled and are not harmful for the environment and human health.

Since it is crucial for practical applications that the coating not only enhances functionality of textiles, but also preserves the fabric's original properties and appearance, while ensuring suitability for use and handling, we first checked the visual appearance of the samples. This involved visual assessment and hand-feel, determining the sample thickness and measuring the colour values. To effectively compare the properties of fabrics, we determined the properties of both untreated (control) and coated fabrics. The visual differences between the untreated and coated CO and PES were minimal (Figure 2a-d). The handfeel of the coated samples was similar to the control ones, although there was a subtle feel of coating presence on the fabric, determined by slightly more textured and stiffer surface. To determine the colour differences quantitatively, CIE L*a*b* colour values of the control and coated CO and PES samples were measured. The results show (Figure 2) that the lightness values (CIE L*) of both control samples are slightly higher than of the belonging coated samples, meaning that by application of the coating, the samples become slightly darker. The values of the green–red colour coordinates (CIE a*) are on the red side of the colour coordinate for CO and PES samples, control and coated ones. After the coating application the values decrease for both CO and PES fabric, which is more evident in the case of cotton samples, meaning that the coated samples are less red than the uncoated ones. The values of the blue–yellow coordinate are on

the blue side of the colour coordinate for all four samples. The biggest difference in the CIE b^* values are seen between control and coated cotton sample, where the CIE b^* value decreases from -15.95 to -5.59 after coating application, meaning that the samples become less blue. This is also noticeable with the naked eye, as coated CO sample is slightly less blue and more yellow than the control one. This small difference in colour values is due to the thin layer of coating that does not significantly affect the sample's appearance. This is also evident from the results of thickness measurements (Figure 2) which show, that with coating application, the thickness increases minimally, by 0,05 mm for CO and by 0,01 mm for PES.

	Control fabric		Coated fabric	
COTTON	a)	Thickness = 0.35 ± 0.01 mm CIE L^* = 97.63 CIE a^* = 2.90 CIE b^* = -15.95	b)	Thickness = 0.40 ± 0.01 mm CIE L^* = 95.81 CIE a^* = 0.85 CIE b^* = -5.59
	c)	Thickness = 0.41 ± 0.00 mm CIE L^* = 92.59 CIE a^* = 5.61 CIE b^* = -22.38	d)	Thickness = 0.42 ± 0.01 mm CIE L^* = 91.28 CIE a^* = 4.23 CIE b^* = -16.80
POLYESTER				

Figure 2: Visual appearance, thickness and CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ values of the control and coated CO and PES.

According to the results above, the coating has minimal influence on the original properties of CO and PES fabric. To check more precisely how the application of coating influences the surface morphology of the fabric, SEM analysis was carried out. SEM micrograph of coated sample (Figure 3b) shows the presence of microcapsules, which are spherical and mostly evenly distributed over the surface of the fabric, with some individual aggregates observed. How their presence influences the water repellency of the coated material in comparison to the control sample, was determined through measuring the static contact angle with water. The hydrophobicity of material is achieved when the water droplets do not spread or wet its surface. The boundary between wetting and repellency is defined by the contact angle of the liquid droplet on the textile substrate. If the contact angle is less than 90° , the textile is wettable, but if the contact angle is greater than 90° , the textile substrate is repellent. In other words, an increase in the contact angle means an increase in repellency (Law, 2014). Our measurements showed that the untreated samples are highly hydrophilic, to the extent that it is not possible to determine a measurable WCA with the standardized procedure. Therefore, the WCA was determined as $<10^\circ$ (Figure 3c). After the coating application the WCA increased to above 120° , meaning that the samples are hydrophobic (Figure 3d), which is also evident from the WCA images.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of a) control PES fabric and b) coated PES fabric at magnification 50x and WCA value with the image of droplet of c) control and d) coated PES fabric.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this research was to produce hydrophobic textile fabric using natural, biodegradable compounds that are safe for human health and environment. Our innovative coating was developed using natural biopolymers in the form of microcapsules. Application of the coating did not significantly alter the appearance, colour or thickness of the CO and PES fabrics. SEM micrographs showed an even distribution of the microcapsules across the fabric surface. The WCA values increased from $< 10^\circ$ for untreated fabric to above 120° for coated fabric, which is comparable to commercial hydrophobic coatings. Unlike fluorine-based coatings, the developed formulation is non-toxic, biodegradable and safe for the environment and human health. In conclusion, this research has shown that hydrophobic properties of textile fabrics can be achieved using biopolymers as renewable sources in an environmentally friendly, sustainable way, which is a much safer alternative to traditional PFAS. Additional analysis has to be performed to determine the coating's durability in comparison with commercial coatings, as this will be crucial for assessing their long-term performance, effectiveness and viability in practical applications.

5. REFERENCES

- Ahrens, L., Bundschuh, M. 2014. "Fate and effects of poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances in the aquatic environment: a review". *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry* 33(9): 1921-1929.
- Bartell, S. M., Vieira, V. M. 2021. "Critical review on PFOA, kidney cancer, and testicular cancer." *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* 71(6): 663-679.
- Blake, B. E., Pinney, S. M., Hines, E. P., et al. 2018. "Associations between longitudinal serum perfluoroalkyl substance (PFAS) levels and measures of thyroid hormone, kidney function, and body mass index in the Fernald Community Cohort." *Environmental pollution* 242: 894-904.
- ChemRadar. 2024. "Japan proposes to designate 138 perfluorinated compounds as Class I Specified Chemical Substances". URL: <https://www.chemradar.com/news/detail/dz1n895bhdz4> (last accessed on 30.1.2025).
- Gaines, L. 2023. "Historical and current usage of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS): A literature review." *Am J Ind Med.* 66: 353–378.
- Gluge, J. et al. 2020. "An overview of the uses of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)." *Environ. Sci.: Processes Impacts* 22: 2345.
- EPA – United States Environmental Protection Agency. Our Current Understanding of the Human Health and Environmental Risks of PFAS. URL: <https://www.epa.gov/pfas/our-current-understanding-human-health-and-environmental-risks-pfas> (last accessed on 19.12.2023).
- Fenton, S. E., et al. 2021. "Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance toxicity and human health review: Current state of knowledge and strategies for informing future research." *Environmental toxicology and chemistry* 40(3): 606-630.

- Jin, H., Xu, W. 2018. "The Preparation and Properties of Fluoroacrylate-Modified Polysiloxane as a Fabric Coating Agent." *Coatings* 8: 31.
- Karášková, P., et al. 2016. "Perfluorinated alkyl substances (PFASs) in household dust in Central Europe and North America." *Environment international* 94: 315-324.
- Kleinman, M.T., Stevenson, E. D. 2021. "Introduction to the 51st Annual A&WMA Critical Review: PFOA and Cancer." *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* 71: 661-662.
- Law, K-Y. 2014. "Definitions for Hydrophilicity, Hydrophobicity, and Superhydrophobicity: Getting the Basics Right." *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* 5(4): 686-688.
- Li, Y., Oliver, P. D., Kookana S. R. 2018. "A critical analysis of published data to discern the role of soil and sediment properties in determining sorption of per and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs)." *Science of the Total Environment* 628-629: 110-120.
- Lin, Y., Jiang, J. J., Rodenburg, L. A., et al. 2020. "Perfluoroalkyl substances in sediments from the Bering Sea to the western Arctic: Source and pathway analysis." *Environment international* 139: 105699.
- Lin, T. C., Lee, D. J. 2021. "Cotton fabrics modified with tannic acid/long-chain alkylamine grafting for oil/water separation." *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers* 127: 367-375.
- Merino, N., Qu, Y., Deeb, A., R., Hawley, E., R., Hoffmann, M. R., Mahendra, S. 2016. "Degradation and Removal Methods for Perfluoroalkyl and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances in Water." *Environmental Engineering Science* 33(9): 615-649.
- Messerschmidt, M. et al. 2018. "Fluorocarbon-Free Dual-Action Textile Finishes Based on Covalently Attached Thermoresponsive Block Copolymer Brush Coatings." *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10: 40088–40099.
- New York State Department of Environmental Conservation. 2023. »PFAS in apparel law.« URL: <https://dec.ny.gov/environmental-protection/help-for-businesses/pfas-in-apparel-law> (last accessed on 30.1.2025)
- OECD, Toward a new comprehensive global database of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs): Summary report on updating the OECD 2007 list of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs). 2018, Environment Directorate.
- Panieri, E., Baralic, K., Djukic-Cosic, D., Buha Djordjevic, A., Saso, L. 2022. "PFAS molecules: a major concern for the human health and the environment." *Toxics* 10(2): 44.
- Sadia, M., Nollen, I., Helmus, R., Laak, T. L., Béen, F., Praetorius, A., van Wezel, A. P. 2023. "Occurrence, Fate, and Related Health Risks of PFAS in Raw and Produced Drinking Water." *Environmental Science Technology* 57(8): 3062–3074.
- Shahid, M., Maiti, S., Adivarekar, R. V., Liu, S. 2022. "Biomaterial based fabrication of superhydrophobic textiles – A review." *Materials today chemistry* 24: 100940.
- Smalling, K. L., Romanok, K. M., et al. 2023. "Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in United States tap water: comparison of underserved private-well and public-supply exposures and associated health implications." *Environment International* 178: 108033.
- Spyrakakis, F., Dragani, T. A. 2023. "The EU's per-and Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) ban: A case of policy over science." *Toxics*, 11(9): 721.
- Wee, S. Y., Aris, A. Z. 2023. "Environmental impacts, exposure pathways, and health effects of PFOA and PFOS." *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 267: 115663.
- Worley, R. R., Moore, S. M., Tierney, B. C., et al. 2017. "Per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances in human serum and urine samples from a residentially exposed community." *Environment international* 106: 135-143.
- Zheng, G., Salamova, A. 2020. "Are Melamine and Its Derivatives the Alternatives for Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance (PFAS) Fabric Treatments in Infant Clothes?" *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54: 10207-10216.

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